

SARCOMA PRIMITIVE RARE DU THORAX: A CASE STUDY AND A REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

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Summary

Synovial sarcoma is a rare malignancy, accounting for 10% of soft tissue sarcomas. Thoracic involvement is rare and varies in location. It usually develops in the limbs and its pulmonary location is exceptional. We report a clinical case of synovial sarcoma of the lung in a 25-year-old male discovered at a localized stage. This tumor, which is extremely rare, has a particular immunohistochemical phenotype, which strongly contributes to diagnosis. Tags: Imaging shows a heterogeneous tumor, invading adjacent structures. The histological diagnosis was made by mediastinal biopsy, revealing synovial sarcoma we discuss the clinical, radiological, histological and therapeutic aspects of this tumor, as well as data from the literature.

INTRODUCTION

Synovial sarcomas are among the most common soft tissue tumors, found in more than 85% of cases around the extremities, especially in the lower limbs. It is a rare tumor of young adults, thoracic localization is rare and mediastinal localization is exceptional. Our goal is to illustrate the imaging aspects through a case that occurred in a young man.

OBSERVATION

This is a young male patient, 25 years old with no pathological history, who complained of chest pain, dry cough complicated by haemoptoid sputum.

The chest radiograph showed a right paracardiac opacity of water tone with polylobed contours, homogeneous without calcification within it, on the frontal incidence, and which projects into the inferior middle mediastinum on the profile incidence (Figure 1).

Figure 1: a. Frontal Chest X-ray: Opacity of the Lower and Anterior Half on the Profile X-ray of the Homogeneous Dense Right Hemi thorax.

The thoraco-abdomino-pelvic CT scan objectified the presence of a voluminous infiltrating mediastinal mass, involving the upper, middle and lower levels, of irregular shape and contour, of tissue density in places and of heterogeneous enhancement largely necrosis, measuring 100 x 100 x 124 mm (T x AP x H), the lesion infiltrated the vascular structures, the pericardium and acardiac cavities: These include the ventricles and atria, the superior vena cava over 180 degrees, the trunk of the pulmonary artery, the right pulmonary artery and the left pulmonary vein. It also infiltrated the anterior wall of the esophagus and the diaphragm and scalocated the hepatic segment IVa. No evidence of pleural effusion or mediastinal lymphadenopathy. And the remote extension balance was negative.

Figure 2: a, b, c. Axial section of a thoracic computed tomography scan in the mediastinal window objectifying a tissue process with middle and inferior mediastinal development, D, the coronal and sagittal section regains a heterogeneous enhancement of the mass, firmly adhering to the heart chambers.

A thoracic MRI found a hila-mediastinal mass, infiltrating the cardiovascular structures, with polylobed contours, of heterogeneous signal and enhancement containing tissue areas in hyposignal T1 and intermediate signal T2 enhancing after injection of Gadolinium, cystic areas of fluid signal in frank hypersignal T2 as well as hemorrhagic foci in hypersignal T1 and T2.

Figure 3: Axial Section e Sequence T (a): mass in Polylobed Hyposignal T1, Coronal Section Sequence T2 in Heterogeneous Mass T2 (b), Axial Section, Sequence T1 with Injection of Contrast Products. Solidocystic Fluid and Haemorrhagic Double-Component Mass (C), Restrictive in Diffusion Sequence (D).

The patient underwent a CT-guided biopsy whose histology revealed a biphasic malignant mesenchymal tumor suggestive of a high-grade synovial sarcoma. The immunohistochemical study was performed using antibodies against AE1, AE3, EMA, CD99, Be12 showing:

- Heterogeneous and multifocal AE1, AE3, EMA expression by tumor cells
- Une expression membraneuse intense et diffuse de CD99 par les cellules néoplasiques
- Une expression hétérogène de Be12 par les cellules tumorales

The patient, who was deemed inoperable after multidisciplinary consultation, was put on chemotherapy.

DISCUSSION

Synovial sarcoma is a tumor of mesenchymal tissue with epithelial differentiation, which most commonly affects the extremities of the limbs, affecting adolescents and young adults between the ages of 15 and 40. Mediastinal localization is exceptional [1]. Mediastinal synovial sarcomas are very aggressive tumors with a high recurrence rate and metastatic risk.

Diagnosis of primary mediastinal synovial sarcoma requires a combination of clinical, radiological, pathological, and immunohistochemical investigations to rule out alternative primary tumors and metastatic sarcoma [3].

Mediastinal synovial sarcoma often manifests itself by non-specific signs due to compression, such as chest pain, cough, fever, dyspnea, which are common findings in many mediastinal tumors [4.5]. Tags:

Our patient also had a non-specific clinical and paraclinical presentation. The radiological manifestations of mediastinal synovial sarcoma are not different from bronchogenic, metastatic carcinoma or other primary lung tumors,

When it comes to imaging tools, chest X-rays are usually the first and least accurate examination performed. It may show ill-defined pulmonary condensation or parenchymal mass, pleural mass, pleural thickening, or almost complete opacification of the hemi thorax. Ipsilateral pleural effusion may be present

CT scan is much more accurate, mediastinal synovial sarcoma usually appears as a well-defined, heterogeneous mass that contains areas of fluid consistent with necrosis or hemorrhage. Similarly, in our patient, he had areas of fluid necrosis that were not enhanced. These tumors tend to present with a large size, in the anterior, middle, or posterior mediastinum, as well as the presence of pericardial infiltration and effusions. Calcifications are lacking in this type. It may show the existence of mediastinal lymphadenopathy which is rare [6.7].

Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) better shows the tumor heterogeneity related to the tumor, hemorrhagic and necrotic contingent in the intralesion: the "triple sign"; associating on the T2-weighted sequence a fluid or hemorrhagic hyper signal, a tissue intermediate signal and a fibrous hypo signal [8.9].

Epithelial membrane antigen (EMA) and Bel2 expression are observed in 90% of synovial sarcoma cases in immunohistochemistry, while CD99 and S100 are observed in 60% and 30% of cases, respectively [10,11]. In our case, immunohistochemistry showed positivity for bcl2 and vimentin. Molecular testing is not necessary if clinical and histological data confirm or suggest the diagnosis of synovial sarcoma [12, 13].

Treatment for synovial sarcoma is mainly based on surgery. The choice of complementary treatment, which may be adjuvant chemotherapy and/or radiotherapy, depends on the patient's age, the quality of the surgical margins, and the size of the tumor [14, 15].

CONCLUSION

Mediastinal synovial sarcoma is a very rare tumor with a poor prognosis, with a tendency to recur locally and metastasize at a distance. X-ray images are not specific, but they point to diagnosis. Chest MRI provides a better understanding of the tissue composition of the tumor, as well as its heterogeneity due to the presence of tumor, hemorrhagic and necrotic areas, forming the "triple sign".

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